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Investments in Fixed Capital Globally

Grew by 32.28% between 2013 and 2022

Gross fixed capital formation as a percentage of GDP represents an economic measure that indicates the total investment in fixed capital in an economy as a percentage of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This metric includes spending on acquiring capital goods such as buildings, infrastructure, machinery, equipment, and land improvements. It is a key indicator of an economy's ability to grow and develop, as a high level of gross capital formation suggests that a country is significantly investing in its future productive resources. Gross capital formation also includes changes in inventories, representing goods produced but not yet sold or used. This aspect reflects short-term demand and supply fluctuations and can influence future production. The percentage relative to GDP allows for comparisons of capital investment between different economies, regardless of the absolute size of GDP. A high percentage of capital formation relative to GDP is generally seen as positive, as it indicates an investment propensity that can lead to greater productive capacity and, therefore, sustained economic growth. However, while a high level of investment can be advantageous, it must be sustainable and supported by effective management and a stable economic environment to translate into long-term economic growth.

Global Fixed Capital Investments in 2022. Gross capital formation as a percentage of GDP in 2022 highlights notable disparities among countries, reflecting different economic priorities, development levels, and investment strategies. Mozambique, with an impressive 100%, leads this list, indicating a massive investment in fixed capital. This could suggest a phase of intense infrastructure construction and machinery acquisition, crucial for long-term economic development. However, it is essential to examine whether such investments are sustainable and whether they are effectively translated into stable economic growth and overall population well-being improvements. Iran and China follow with percentages of 73.9% and 68.3%, respectively. In particular, China has maintained a strong fixed capital investment strategy for decades, fueling its rapid economic growth and industrial transformation. Such high levels of investment have been crucial for developing infrastructure and technological modernization, although they have also raised concerns about debt sustainability and resource allocation effectiveness. Nepal, Algeria, Uzbekistan, and Mongolia, with percentages ranging from 60.9% to 66.3%, also show a significant commitment to expanding fixed capital. These countries, many of which are developing, seem to be focusing on infrastructure investments to stimulate economic growth. For example, Algeria, with its 65.5%, might focus on developing its natural resources and building the necessary infrastructure to support such activities. Countries like Tanzania, Bahrain, and Senegal, with gross capital formation percentages between 51.6% and 56.2%, reflect economies in transformation, where investments are crucial to supporting economic growth. Bahrain, a small but wealthy Gulf country, is likely investing heavily in infrastructure to diversify its economy beyond oil. Similarly, Tanzania and Senegal, both African countries, might be in the phase of enhancing infrastructure to promote economic development and improve living conditions. The case of Panama and South Korea, with percentages of 48.8% and 48.5%, suggests economies that are seeking to sustain their growth through continuous fixed capital investments. South Korea, in particular, is known for its advanced technological and industrial development, and a high rate of

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capital formation aligns with its strategy to maintain a globally competitive economy. Vietnam and Indonesia, with 46.8%, show rapidly growing Asian countries that are investing significantly in their economies to maintain their growth momentum. Vietnam, in particular, has seen impressive economic growth in recent years, driven by economic reforms and high export demand. Estonia, with 46.5%, represents an example of a small European country investing heavily in fixed capital, probably to strengthen its digital and technological economy, being one of the world's leaders in e-governance. India, with 43.5%, despite its large population and economic growth, reflects a significant but not exceptionally high level of capital formation. This might indicate that while there are important infrastructure investments, there are still areas for improvement to support more robust and inclusive economic growth. Moving to countries like Germany and France, with percentages of 29.6% and 35.9%, respectively, we see developed economies that maintain a moderate level of fixed capital investments. These levels, although lower compared to emerging countries, probably reflect an already achieved economic and infrastructural stability, where the emphasis might be more on maintenance and upgrading rather than building new infrastructure. The United States, with 27.3%, shows a relatively low percentage, which can reflect a combination of factors such as a mature economy, an advanced financial market that facilitates private investment, and possibly a greater emphasis on non-capital-intensive sectors like services and technology. Finally, countries with very low percentages, such as Greece (14.3%), Lithuania (13.2%), and South Africa (13.1%), indicate economies that might face significant challenges in terms of investment. These low levels of capital formation could result from economic crises, political instability, or budget constraints that limit the ability to invest in new infrastructure and fixed capital. In conclusion, gross capital formation as a percentage of GDP offers a clear indication of a country's investment priorities and economic development strategy. High investment levels are generally seen as positive for long-term growth, but it is crucial that these investments are sustainable and well-managed. The variability among countries reflects a range of economic strategies and development levels, providing insight into the different challenges and opportunities each country faces. Analyzing this data can provide valuable insights into future economic growth prospects and the potential for sustainable development globally.

Global Fixed Capital Investments between 2013 and 2022. Analyzing gross capital formation as a percentage of GDP for the period 2013-2022 highlights various economic dynamics among countries, reflecting both significant successes and complex challenges. Starting with the countries that showed the greatest increase, Angola stands out with an impressive growth of 788.57%, rising from 3.5% of GDP in 2013 to 31.1% in 2022. This massive increase can be attributed to a series of factors, including significant investments in infrastructure and the energy sector, aimed at leveraging the country's natural resources to stimulate economic development. Similarly, Côte d'Ivoire saw a remarkable increase of 616.28%, from a modest 4.3% to 30.8%. This might reflect a period of political stability and economic reforms that attracted foreign investments and supported capital growth. Brunei registered an increase of 585.33%, rising from 7.5% to 51.4%. This significant increase can be seen as a strategy to diversify the economy beyond the oil sector, investing heavily in infrastructure and development projects. Malta and Cyprus also showed significant increases of 418.97% and 352.31%, respectively, suggesting a period of strong economic development and attraction of foreign investments, probably also related to the tourism and financial services sectors. Mozambique showed an increase of 258.42%, rising from 27.9% to 100%. This incredible leap can be explained by massive investments in extraction projects and infrastructure, often supported by foreign investments, particularly from China. However, this level of investment raises questions about sustainability and effectiveness in creating lasting economic value. Other countries also showed significant increases, such as Pakistan (219.61%), Kuwait (197.10%), and Iceland (189.52%). For Pakistan, this increase could reflect concerted efforts to improve infrastructure and attract foreign investments, despite economic and political challenges. Kuwait, with a growth of 197.10%, has probably invested significantly in an attempt to diversify its economy beyond the oil sector. Iceland, for its part, saw an

increase of 189.52%, suggesting a sustained economic recovery and expansion after the 2008 financial crisis. On the other hand, some countries saw a significant decrease in gross capital formation as a percentage of GDP. Among these, Kenya showed one of the most dramatic decreases, dropping from 22.9% to 12.1%, a reduction of 47.16%. This decline could be attributed to a combination of factors, including political instability, governance issues, and economic difficulties that hindered investments. Namibia registered a decrease of 52.66%, dropping from 41.4% to 19.6%. This could reflect a series of economic problems, including a reduction in mining investments and budget issues. Armenia saw a reduction of 53%, from 38.3% to 18%, perhaps indicative of a decrease in foreign investments and internal economic problems. Ukraine showed one of the most significant reductions, with a drop of 57.06%, falling from 16.3% to 7%. This drastic decline is certainly influenced by the ongoing war with Russia, which has devastated the economy and drastically reduced investments. Tunisia registered a decrease of 57.59%, from 29% to 12.3%, probably reflecting political instability and economic challenges post-revolution. Finally, the case of Mozambique, which saw an extraordinary increase of 258.42%, raises questions about the sustainability of such investments. While such a significant increase can indicate a period of rapid capital construction, it is essential to assess whether these investments have been well-managed and whether they have led to tangible improvements in quality of life and sustainable economic growth. In conclusion, the analysis of gross capital formation as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2022 reveals a complex and varied landscape. Countries like Angola, Côte d'Ivoire, Brunei, and Malta have shown spectacular increases, likely due to a combination of foreign investments, political stability, and economic reforms. However, countries like Kenya, Namibia, Armenia, Ukraine, and Tunisia have seen significant reductions, often due to political instability, economic problems, and reduced investments. These data highlight the importance of a stable political and economic environment and good governance to sustain capital investment and promote sustainable economic growth.

Economic Policies to Increase the Value of Gross Capital Formation as a Percentage of GDP. Increasing the value of gross capital formation as a percentage of GDP is a crucial goal for many economies, especially those developing and in transition, as it represents a way to stimulate long-term economic growth, improve infrastructure, and increase productivity. To achieve this goal, a series of well-thought-out and coordinated economic policies is necessary. One of the first policies to consider is creating a stable macroeconomic environment. Economic stability means controlling inflation, maintaining reasonable interest rates, and ensuring prudent fiscal management. A stable economic environment reduces uncertainty, which is essential for attracting both domestic and foreign investments. Businesses and investors are more likely to invest in infrastructure, machinery, and other forms of fixed capital when they can predict their investment returns with greater certainty. Another crucial policy is improving the institutional and regulatory framework. This involves reforming investment-related laws, making them more transparent and less bureaucratic. Simple and fast procedures for obtaining licenses and permits can reduce the costs and time required to start new investment projects. Moreover, an effective and reliable judicial system that protects property rights and enforces contracts is fundamental for building investor confidence. Attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) is another key element to increase gross capital formation. Governments can adopt specific policies to attract FDI, such as offering tax incentives, creating special economic zones, and signing bilateral investment agreements. Special economic zones, in particular, can offer high-quality infrastructure, favorable tax regimes, and simplified access to foreign markets, creating an ideal environment for industrial and technological investments. Investing in education and workforce training is another critical factor. A well-trained and skilled workforce is more productive and attracts greater investments in fixed capital. Governments should therefore promote educational policies that improve the technical and professional skills of the population. Vocational training programs, incentives for continuous learning, and collaborations between educational institutions and industry can help bridge the gap between the skills offered and those demanded by the labor market. Infrastructure is a fundamental component of gross capital formation. Investing in quality

infrastructure such as roads, railways, ports, airports, and telecommunications networks can significantly increase economic productivity and attract investments. Governments can finance such investments through a combination of direct public spending, public-private partnerships, and international loans. Effective planning and execution of infrastructure projects are essential to ensure these investments produce maximum economic benefits. The financial sector plays a crucial role in facilitating capital formation. A solid and well-regulated banking system, along with developed capital markets, can provide the necessary resources to finance fixed capital investments. Policies should aim to improve access to credit, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises, which often have difficulty obtaining financing. Promoting deep and liquid capital markets, including stock exchanges and bond markets, can also provide alternative channels for raising capital. Technological innovation and research and development (R&D) are essential components for increasing capital formation. Governments can incentivize R&D through grants, tax credits, and direct support to research and development institutions. Encouraging the adoption of new technologies in companies can increase productivity and stimulate further investments in fixed capital. Policies should also promote collaboration between universities, research centers, and the private sector to develop and commercialize technological innovations. An open trade policy can stimulate capital formation by allowing companies to access larger markets and more diverse resources. Reducing trade barriers, participating in regional and international trade agreements, and promoting exports can create opportunities for companies to grow and invest in new capital. Greater integration into global markets can also attract foreign direct investment, which often brings with it technology transfer and advanced managerial skills. Environmental sustainability is a growing aspect of economic policies. Investing in green technologies and sustainable infrastructure not only addresses pressing climate challenges but can also stimulate new economic sectors and create jobs. Policies must incentivize the use of renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable business practices. Governments can also promote the adoption of environmental standards in construction and transportation, ensuring that economic growth does not compromise natural resources. Governance and transparency are fundamental to creating an investment-friendly environment. Corruption and lack of transparency can significantly reduce investor confidence and increase investment costs. Reforms aimed at improving transparency, strengthening law enforcement, and combating corruption are essential. Governments must implement good governance practices, including transparent public budgets, open procurement procedures, and effective control mechanisms. Finally, adapting fiscal policies can incentivize capital formation. Governments can offer tax incentives for fixed capital investments, such as accelerated depreciation, investment tax credits for new equipment and infrastructure, and tax reductions for companies that reinvest their profits. These fiscal measures can make fixed capital investments more attractive for companies, thus stimulating economic growth. In summary, increasing gross capital formation as a percentage of GDP requires a holistic approach involving macroeconomic stability, improvement of the regulatory framework, attraction of foreign investments, skill development, infrastructure investment, financial sector development, promotion of innovation, open trade policies, environmental sustainability, good governance, and fiscal incentives. Each country must adapt these policies to its specific economic and social circumstances, but the ultimate goal remains to create an environment that favors productive investments and stimulates sustainable and inclusive economic growth.

Conclusions. The value of fixed capital investments as a percentage of GDP grew by 32.28% between 2013 and 2022, rising from 25.6 units to 33.9 units. Some countries have seen the value of fixed capital investments as a percentage of GDP grow above the average, namely: Angola with +788.57%, Côte d'Ivoire with +616.28%, Brunei Darussalam with +585.33%, Malta with +418.97%, Cyprus with 352.31%. There are countries where the value of fixed capital investments as a percentage of GDP has decreased significantly, namely Namibia with -52.66%, Armenia with -53.00%, Ukraine with -57.06%, Tunisia with -57.59%, Guinea with -61.03%.

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